

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of Suntan Lotion From Mung Bean (*Vigna Radiata*) Extract

Ashwini Pandav¹, Nilesh Chougule², Suchay Bangar*³

¹ Assistant Professor. Ashokrao Mane Institute of Pharmacy, Ambap, Dist. Kolhapur, Maharashtra India, 416112

² Principal. Ashokrao Mane Institute of Pharmacy, Ambap, Dist. Kolhapur, Maharashtra India, 416112

³ Student of B. Pharm, Ashokrao Mane Institute of Pharmacy, Ambap, Dist. Kolhapur, Maharashtra India, 416112

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 06 Aug 2024

Accepted: 11 Aug 2024

Published: 18 Aug 2024

Keywords:

Suntan, Skin Burn, UV Radiation, *Vigna radiata*(L), Sun Protection, Mung bean.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13337517

ABSTRACT

Suntan lotion is a preparation that protects you from UV rays. ultraviolet (UV) rays are what causes sunburn, but ultraviolet (UV) A rays may be more harmful to the skin. Sunblock Should ideally obstruct both wavelengths. This study's objective was to create a topical suntan lotion recipe using a set of fixed oils along with a few therapeutic drugs. Suntan lotion could be chemicals, either organic or inorganic. The item either reflects or absorbs solar energy. UV radiation and offers skin protection. The growing frequency of skin cancers and the consequences of photodamage due to UV radiation. Suntan lotion ingredients should be non-toxic, non-irritating, chemically inert, photostable, and capable of providing total defense of the skin against solar damage radiation. Mung bean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek) is one of the plants that rich in antioxidant compound. Antioxidant is a compound that can inhibit the skin aging process because of photoaging. The green gram (*Vigna radiata* L. Wilczek), also known as Mudga in Sanskrit, is regarded by Ayurvedic science as the best pulse and one of the healthiest foods that may be regularly consumed to maintain health. Diabetes is a chronic lifestyle condition that may be controlled with diet, exercise, and contemporary medications like insulin and oral hypoglycemic medicines. In Ayurvedic medicine, green grams are advised as both a dietetic food and a medication for diabetes. The phytochemistry of *Vigna radiata*, or mung beans, demonstrates its antidiabetic qualities, and a number of research using green gramme extracts have validated the capacity of mung bean to control insulin resistance and reduce blood glucose levels.

***Corresponding Author:** Suchay Bangar

Address: Student of B. Pharm, Ashokrao Mane Institute of Pharmacy, Ambap, Dist. Kolhapur, Maharashtra India, 416112

Email ✉: suchaybangar@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

INTRODUCTION

Sunlight is a source of energy for human needs. In addition, the sun also contains ultraviolet (UV) rays that cannot be seen and felt directly by humans. UV rays have good benefits for health, one of which is the formation of cholecalciferol Vitamin D3 [1]. However, if exposed to excess can harm skin health, which will experience changes in structure and composition that cause oxidative stress to the skin. The negative impact that is felt in the short term is in the form of changes in pigmentation, erythema and photosensitivity, while in the long term, it can cause skin cancer and premature ageing [2]. Therefore, several ways are needed to protect the skin from the dangers of UV rays, including wearing protective clothing, consuming antioxidants (both inside and outside the body) and wearing sunscreen [3]. Thus, researchers are interested in making suntan a solution to protect the skin from the dangers of UV rays. Most suntan products still use synthetic compounds such as titanium dioxide. Synthetic compounds, when used continuously, can damage one's health. So that the cosmetic industry is currently intensively seeking and developing products that are oriented towards natural ingredients because they are classified as safe to use so that many people respond positively. One of the natural ingredients used to make suntan lotion products is which mung bean a very high antioxidant content. Cosmetics are described as "articles supposed to be rubbed, Poured, sprinkled, or sprayed on, delivered into, or otherwise Carried out to the human frame or any component thereof for cleansing, beautifying, selling attractiveness, or changing the appearance" [4] Among the generally used cosmetics are suntan lotion. These are formulations which might be carried out onto the pores and skin floor to Defend it from the dangerous results of ultraviolet (UV) mild. Repeated publicity of the pores and skin has been related to an excessive risk of growing pores

and skin cancers. According to most cancers studies USA, eight out Of 10 instances of cancer might be avoided thru an under status of the dangerous results of daylight and a way to defend oneself from the dangerous rays.[5] Sunrays encompass an array of wavelengths stages that fluctuate in Frequency and their electricity profiles. The suns electromagnetic Spectrum includes cosmic rays, gamma rays, X-rays, UV rays, Microwaves, and radio waves in lowering order of electricity. Among Those cosmic, gamma and X rays are correctly filtered out of the Earth via way of means of the surroundings and consequently gift no capability for Inflicting harm. It is, however, noteworthy that they may be the Deadliest and publicity could result in failures of epic proportions. The UV rays can penetrate the earth' surroundings as can the rest of the decrease electricity spectrums. Microwaves and radio waves are Now no longer of clinical significance as pertains to inflicting pores and skin harm. The Recognition of this newsletter is as a consequence the UV spectrum of mild [6]. mung bean is one of the plants that rich in antioxidant compound. Flavonoid compounds contained in mung bean, vitexin and is vitexin, have an antioxidant effect. Vitexin inhibits DPPH radicals of approximately 60% at 100 gm/ml and effectively inhibits UV rays that can stimulate skin cell death [7]. Skin aging can be caused by UV radiation (photoaging) which trigger in the formation of ROS (Reactive Oxygen Species) free radical on the skin. Free radicals cause oxidative damage to the tissue known as oxidative stress [8,9]. The mung bean (*Vigna radiata*) is also having the antiaging property. Skin aging is basically caused due the photoaging radiation.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM

UV radiation is essential for human health because it aids absorption in the intestine for the production of calcium, phosphorus and vitamin D3. On the

other hand, this radiation also damages our health, acting directly on DNA, RNA proteins, lipids and thus causing possible carcinogenic effects. The most effective way to protect the skin harmful UV radiation is the local application of any active molecule with UV radiation absorptive or reflective properties. Therefore, the importance of suntan product has increased current scenario. [10] Using suntan lotion is one of the best – and easiest – ways to protect your skin and appearance and health at any age. With regular use, suntan lotion helps prevent sunburn, skin cancer and premature aging.

OBJECTIVES

- To carry out detailed literature review of the sunscreen lotion and mung bean with regard to its activities.
- To formulation and evaluation etc.
- To prepare a suntan lotion formulation.
- To Evaluation of prepared lotion

- To Stability study of formulations.

DRUG PROFILE

Synonym:

Mung bean, green gram.

Biological Source:

Dried seeds which is obtained from the legume plant. Belonging to the family Fabaceae.

The mung bean is likely native to the Indian subcontinent and is widely cultivated in Asian for use in a variety of sweet and savory dishes, particularly in India, China, Korea, Thailand. They contain flavonoids and polyphenols that gives antioxidant properties. Vigna Radiata seed extract is a rare cosmetic ingredient.

Properties:

- Antioxidant
- Antidiabetic
- Antiaging drug
- Anti-inflammatory

Pharmacological activities of Vigna Radiata

Mung bean is well known as green gram or moong bean. Mung bean has been consumed as a common traditional food worldwide for more than 3500 years. [26]

Anti-oxidant Activity:

- Antioxidant activity the seeds, sprouts, and hulls of mung beans contain an enormous amount of macro (protein, polypeptides, oligo, and polysaccharides) and micronutrients (flavonoids, phenolic acids, organic acids, sterols, triterpenes, aldehydes), which exerts potent antioxidant properties.
- Antioxidant activity the seeds, sprouts, and hulls of mung beans contain an enormous amount of macro (protein, polypeptides, oligo, and polysaccharides) and micronutrients (flavonoids, phenolic acids, organic acids, sterols, triterpenes, aldehydes), which exerts potent antioxidant properties. aerobic respiration and biochemical metabolism [27,28]
- Mung bean sprouts have higher antioxidant potential than raw seeds. It possesses a higher quantity of secondary metabolites [29]. The total antioxidant activity of mung bean sprouts on the 8 th day has significantly elevated six times more than that of dried mung bean seeds as determined by radical scavenging activities of DPPH, ABST, and FRAP [30,31].

Antidiabetic Activity:

The consumption of mung bean has been reported as a potential antidiabetic agent. An experimental animal study showed that the effect of fermented and non-fermented mung bean extracts on normoglycemic, glucose-induced hyperglycemic and alloxan-induced hyperglycemic effects, caused no significant hypoglycemic effect and significantly lowered the blood sugar level in glucose and alloxan-induced hyperglycemic mice [32]

Antihypertensive Activity:

Antihyperlipidemic and antihypertensive effect Metabolic syndrome is the name of a group of disorders that is connected with the risk of high levels of blood glucose, TG, LDL, low levels of HDL, which leads to high possibilities of threats to diabetes, hypertension, obesity, and CVD [33-34]. The regular intake of beans in the food is known to be beneficial for healthy and hypercholesterolemic which subjects by decreasing in the serum TC, TG, and LDL and increase HDL [35].

Antimicrobial Activity:

Antimicrobial activity the utility of bioactive compounds from food legumes as natural antimicrobial agents are commonly known as biocides. Mung bean sprouts have potent antiviral and prophylactic activities against respiratory syncytial virus and Herpes Simplex virus –1, and these activities were comparable with Acyclovir. The underlying mechanism was attributed to active components of mung bean sprouts potentially induce antiviral cytokines in human cells and thereby nullify the actions on viral proliferation [36]

Anti-inflammatory Activity:

Anti-inflammatory effects Mung beans have been consumed in several cuisines and in traditional medicine to treat heat stroke connected with thirst, irritation, and high body temperature, detoxification, and these health promoting effects of mung bean seeds and sprouts are believed to be associated with the inflammatory response in Asian countries [37]. Experimental studies associated with modulation of inflammatory effects by mung bean have been well established. In one of the studies, high-fat diet induced obesity mice with the extract of mung bean seeds significantly reduced lipopolysaccharide-stimulated peritoneal macrophages and inflammation-related parameters (TNF-, IL-1 , IL-6, nitric oxide synthase, COX-2, and NF-B), and alleviated the symptoms of obesity, colitis, and colon inflammation [38]

Anticancer Activity:

Epidemiological studies have also suggested that the intake of beans reduces the prevalence of cancers including colon, breast, prostate, and adenocarcinoma [39–41]. The data obtained from 41 countries and documented that the higher consumption of beans reduced the mortality rate by breast, colon, and prostate cancer [39]. The consumption of beans more than twice a week was linked with markedly decreased (47%) the risk of colon cancer [40] and prostate cancer [41]. It was found that regular intake of beans in rats decreased

azomethane induced tumor morphology by almost 50% [42]. The feeding of cooked bean powder in rats markedly reduced (67%) incidence of breast cancer [43]. Similarly, the diets fed with beans reduce the total tumor incidence and adenocarcinoma incidence by 54% and 75%, respectively [44]. Mung beans contain resistant starch, dietary fibers, phenolic compounds, and micro constituents such as phytic acid, vitexin, isovitexin, protease inhibitors and saponins, which are highly associated with antioxidant and anticarcinogenic properties [44,45]

MATERIAL AND EQUIPMENTS**Table No 1: List of Chemicals**

Sr. No.	Chemicals	Manufacturer
1	Ethanol	Chemistry Laboratory
2	Vigna Radiata extract	Laboratory
3	Stearic Acid	Chemistry Laboratory
4	Triethanolamine	Chemistry Laboratory
5	Liquid Paraffin	Chemistry Laboratory
6	Glycerin	Chemistry Laboratory
7	Methyl Paraben	Chemistry Laboratory
8	Perfuming Agent	Chemistry Laboratory
9	Distilled Water	Chemistry Laboratory

Table No 2: List of Instruments

Sr. No.	Instruments	Manufacturer
1	Electronic analytical weighing balance	LABMAN
2	Electrical water bath	LABLINE
3	pH meter	LABMAN
4	Brookfield Viscometer (LVDV-60)	LABMAN
5	Heating mantel	LABLINE
6	Beaker	LABMAN
7	Stirrer	LABMAN

EXTRACTION OF VIGNA RADIATA:

Maceration was one of the extraction methods used for the extraction of Vigna Radiata.[11] Mung bean was extracted by maceration method using ethanol 96%. 200 g of dried mung bean powder was weighed and extracted in 100 ml of 96% ethanol for 24 hours then filtered until filtrate is obtained. The treatment was carried out for 2 days. The filtrate was collected and evaporated using a rotary evaporator at temperature of 40-50

°C until the ethanol extract was ± 50 ml. [12] Extraction of mung bean powder was done by maceration method using ethanol 96%. The method is chosen to avoid damage of active substances due to heating. Ethanol 96% was used to extract polar substance like flavonoid. Active substances taken from mung bean powder are flavonoids which has an antioxidant effect [13]

METHOD OF FORMULATION SUNTAN LOTION:

Prepare tools and materials, weighed all the materials needed. Separate the ingredients into two groups, namely the oil phase and the water phase. The oil phase consists of stearic acid, liquid paraffin (mass I). The aqueous phase consisted of glycerin, TEA and methyl paraben (dissolved in hot water at 70°C) (mass II). Put mass I into a hot

mortar, then add mass II little by little, grind until a lotion mass is formed. After taking the form of a lotion mass, the extract of Vigna Radiata (Mung Bean) was added little by little, adding perfume while grinding, until homogeneous. Concentration was varied into 3 comparisons (5), (3), and (7) part of Vigna Radiata [14].

Concentration (gm)				
Components	F1	F2	F3	F4
Vigna radiata extract	-----	5 ml	3 ml	7 ml
Stearic Acid	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Triethanolamine	1	1	1	1
Liquid Paraffin	7	7	7	7
Glycerin	5	5	5	5
Methyl Paraben	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Perfume	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S
Distilled water	100ml	100ml	100ml	100ml

EVALUATION OF LOTION:

Physical parameters:

Color:

The color of formulation was checked manually and observed.

Odour:

The Smell of Formulation was checked by applying preparation on hand and feel the fragrance.

Appearance:

Visually checked the appearance of the formulation.

Determination of pH:

The pH of sunscreens was determined using a digital pH meter. pH was measured after 1 g of the formulation was dissolved in 100 ml of newly prepared distilled water for 2 hours. The purpose of this study was to guarantee that the pH of the produced herbal sunscreens is similar to the pH of the skin after 24 hours of use. The results were triple-checked, and S.D. was recorded.

Determination of Viscosity:

The Brookfield viscometer was used to test viscosity, with the proper number of spindles Selected. A 50 ml beaker was used to hold 50 g of preparation until the spindle groove was Dipped

and the rpm was set. Sunscreen viscosity was measured at 5, 10, 20, 50, and 100 Rpm. The viscosity was computed using the factor obtained from the reading. [15]

Spreadability:

The spread ability of sunscreens determined their therapeutic efficiency. The appropriate amount of sunscreen was applied between two slides, and under specified Load directions, and the two sides took the time in seconds to slide off. Spreadability was Defined as the amount of time it took to separate two slides in less time. The formula for calculating it is:

$$S = M \times L / t$$

Where, M = weight tied to the upper slide L = length of glass slide T = time taken to separate the slides. [16]

Washability:

This test is carried out by simply washing applied sunscreen with Water. [17]

Homogeneity:

The formulation was tested for homogeneity by visual appearance and touch. [18]

Irritancy Test:

Mark an area (one sq. cm) on the left-hand dorsal surface. The lotion was applied to the specified

area and time was noted. Irritancy, erythema, edema was checked if any for regular interval up to 24 hrs. and reported. [19]

Stability Testing:

Stability testing of prepared formulation was conducted at room temp, studied for 7 days. And then the formulation was studied at $45 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 days. The formulation was kept both at room and elevated temperature and observed on 5th 10th, 15th and 20th day for all the evaluation parameters.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

1. Physical Parameter of Lotion:

Table No. 4 Physical Parameter

No.	Formula	Color	Shape
1	F1	White	Semi Solid
2	F2	White	Semi Solid
3	F3	White	Semi Solid
4	F4	White	Semi Solid

Determination of pH:

Table No. 5 Determination of pH

No.	Formula	Average
1	F1	5.5
2	F2	5.9
3	F3	6.3
4	F4	5.9

Irritancy test:

In the irritancy test no Redness, Itchy, Rash, Swollen condition seen.

DISCUSSION:

Organoleptic test Organoleptic formulations are very important as an aesthetic value to attract the attention and interest of consumers [20]. The resulting lotion meets the requirements of the color derived from the mung bean. Homogeneity tests the homogeneity of the formulations of extracts of vigna radiata showed that all substances were well distributed in semi-solid dosage forms, with uniform color, no lumps were obtained on the glass object, and there was no separation between the aqueous phase, oil phase and extract used. All body lotion formulations produce homogeneous preparations. Homogeneous body lotion will be evenly distributed, so that when applied to the

body provides the properties of the substances contained in the formulation so that it is easily absorbed into the skin and provides a moisturizing effect on the skin more quickly [21]. pH test Formulation with a pH that matches the skin's pH does not irritate the skin when used. If the pH of the body lotion is low, it can irritate the skin, otherwise if the pH of the preparation is too high, it will cause the skin to become dry. The results of the pH test on all lotion formulations showed that they met the standard not less than 4.5 and not more than 6.5 [22,23]. Viscosity The viscosity for body lotion required by the Indonesian National Standard 16-4399-1996 is 2,000 cp (centipoise) - 50,000 cp (centipoise). It can be seen that the lotion preparations of vigna radiata meet the requirements for viscosity value, a good viscosity greatly affects the effectiveness of a preparation because a lotion that is too runny will give a long enough time to absorb into the skin so that the lotion preparation will take longer to provide a moisturizing effect. on the skin and does not fall into good viscosity if the lotion is too runny [24,25].

CONCLUSION:

Due to increased awareness of the need for protection from harmful UVA and UVB rays, there is a significant market potential for sunscreen chemicals, whether they are synthetic, natural, or a combination of both. A minimum ideal requirement for a sunscreen product would be photo stabilized, uniform, UVA/UVB protection with a high SPF. However, natural chemicals such as polyphenols (flavonoids, tannins), carotenoids, anthocyanidins, certain vitamins, fixed oils, and volatile from vegetables, fruits, medicinal plant parts (leaves, flowers, fruits, berries), algae, and lichens are more effective because of their long-term beneficial effects, particularly against free radical generated skin damaging in addition to blocking UV rays. These sunscreens with natural chemicals added could offer reasonably priced,

genuinely broad-spectrum protection with anti-oxidant, wound healing, anti-inflammatory, and numerous other skin-benefiting properties. benefits of protection.

REFERENCES

1. Pratiwi S, Husni P 2017 Potential use of Indonesian plant phytoconstituents as active sunscreen ingredients *Pharmacy Journal* 15(4) 18-25
2. Tahir I, Jumina, dan Yuliasuti 2002 In vitro and in vivo analysis of UV protection activity of several cinnamic ester compounds as products of the condensation reaction of substituted benzaldehyde and alkyl acetate *Journal of Pharmacy Science and Community (JFSK)* 2(3)136
3. Suryanto B, Syarief SH 2013 Sunscreen activity test of gold nanoparticles octyl p-methoxy cinnamate (opms) as a cosmetic ingredient *Journal of Chemistry* 2(3) 32-37
4. FDA, 2018a. Federal food drug and cosmetic act.
5. Jou, P.C., Tomecki, K.J., 2014. Sunscreens in the United States: current status and Future outlook. *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.* 810, 464–484
6. Rezende, S.G., Dourado, J.G., Amorim De Lino, F.M., Vinhal, D.C., Silva, E.C., Gil, E.D.S., 2014. Methods used in evaluation of the sun protection factor (SPF) of Sunscreens. *Rev. Eletro nica Farma cia*
7. Cao, D et al, (2011) ‘Antioxidant Properties of the Mung Bean Flavonoids on Alleviating Heat Stress’, *Plos One*, 6 (6), pp. 1-9, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0021071.
8. Masaki, H. (2010) ‘Role of antioxidants in the skin: Anti-aging effects’, *Journal of Dermatological Science*, 58 (2), pp. 85-90, doi: 10.1016/j.jdermsci.2010.03.003.
9. Pham-Huy, L. A., He, H., and Pham-Huy, C. (2008) ‘Free radicals, antioxidants in diseases and health’, *International Journal of Biomedical Sciences*, 4 (2), pp. 89-96
10. COLIPA (2006) ;COLIPA Guidelines: International Sun Protection Factor (SPF) Test Method[11] Tiwari,P., Kumar, B., Kaur, M., Kaur, G., Kaur, H. (2011) ‘Phytochemical screening and extraction:A Review’, *International Pharmaceutica Scientia*, 1 (1), pp. 98-106.
11. Patihul Husni1,* Formulation of Peel-off Gel Mask Containing Mung Bean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek) Extract Vol 1, Issue 2, 2019
12. Tang, D., Y.Dong, H. Ren, L. Li, and C. He. (2014) ‘A review of phytochemistry, metabolite changes, and medicinal uses of the common food mung bean and its sprouts (*Vigna radiata* (L). R. Wilczek), *Chemistry Central Journal*, 8 (4), pp. 1-9, doi: 10.1186/1752-153X-8-4.
13. Evi Ekayanti Ginting Preparation of Moisturizing Lotion from Combination Extract of *Clitoria ternatea* Flower and Dragon Fruit Peel “*Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*” 2022; 12(3-S):81-86
14. Government of Indian Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, Part 1, Volume 1, 1st edition. The Controller of publications, New Delhi, 2001
15. Ruby AJ, Kuttan G, Babu KD, Rajasekharan KN, Kuttan R.; Anti-tumour and antioxidant activity Of natural curcuminoids. *Cancer Lett.* 1995;94(1):79-83
16. Selvam R, Subramanian L, Gayathri R, Angayarkanni N; The anti-oxidant activity of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*). *J Ethnopharmacol.* 1995;47(2):59-67
17. Ahmady A, Amini MH, Zhakfar AM, Babak G, Sediqi MN; Sun Protective Potential and Physical Stability of Herbal Sunscreen Developed from Afghan Medicinal Plants. *Turk J Pharm Sci.* 2020;17(3):285-92. Doi:10.4274/tjps.galenos.2019.15428

18. Snehal S Kulkarni, Rasika D Bhalke, V V Pande, Prakash N Kendre. Herbal Plants In Poto Protection And Sun Screening Action: An Overview, Indo American Journal Of Parm. Research. 2014; 4(02). 110
19. Khoirunisa I, Masruriati E, Wicaksono W, "Formulation of Ethanol Extract Cream for Red dragon Fruit Skin (*Hylocereus Polyrhizus*) and Bacterial Activity Test (*Staphylococcus Aureus*)", J Pharmacy, 2018;7(2):54–61.
20. Leny, Fitri K, Marantina R, Ginting PA, Syamsul D, Hafiz I, "The Moisturizing Sheet Mask Formulation of Black Soybean (*Glycine soja*) Ethanolic Extract", International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 2020; 29(4):9045-9051.
21. Leny, Ginting EE, Hafiz I, "Formulation and Evaluation of Candlenut (*Aleurites moluccana* L.) Oil in Gel Preparation", Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development, 2020; 8(5): 41-43. doi.org/10.22270/ajprd.v8i5.84
22. Ginting I, et al, "Utilization of Ambon Banana Stem (*Musa paradisiaca* var. *sapientum* (L)) Ethanol Extract as Moisturizing Sheet Mask, Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics", 2022; 12(2-s):25-29.
23. skandar B, Sidabutar SE, Leny, "Formulasi dan Evaluasi Lotion Ekstrak Alpukat (*Persea americana*) sebagai Pelembab Kulit", Jurnal Islamic Pharmacy, 2021; 6(1):14-21
24. Khoirunisa I, Masruriati E, Wicaksono W, "Formulation of Ethanol Extract Cream for Red dragon Fruit Skin (*Hylocereus Polyrhizus*) and Bacterial Activity Test (*Staphylococcus Aureus*)", J Pharmacy, 2018;7(2):54–6
25. C.J.Lambrides, I. Gongwin Mungbean in: C. Kole(ed) ,Genome Mapping and Molecular Breeding in plants pulses, sugar and tuber crops vol.3, Springer, Berlin,2007,pp.69-90
26. P Y. Lin, H.M. Lai, Bioactive compounds in legumes and their germinated products, J. Agric. Food Chem. 54 (2006) 3807–3814.
27. S. Wongsiri, T. Ohshima, K. Duangmal, Chemical composition: amino acid profile and antioxidant activities of germinated mung beans (*Vigna radiata*), J. Food Process. Preserv. 39 (2015) 1956–1964.
28. D.K. Kim, S.C. Jeong, S. Gorinstein, S.U. Chon, Total polyphenols: antioxidant and antiproliferative activities of different extracts in mung bean seeds and sprouts, Plant Foods Hum. Nutr. 67 (2012) 71–75.
29. X. Guo, T. Li, K. Tang, R.H. Liu, Effect of germination on phytochemical profiles and antioxidant activity of mung bean sprouts (*Vigna radiata*), J. Agric. Food Chem. 60 (2012) 11050–11055.
30. J.H. Lee, J.K. Jeon, S.G. Kim, S.H. Kim, T. Chun, J.Y. Imm, Comparative analyses of total phenols flavonoids, saponins and antioxidant activity in yellow soy beans and mung beans, Int. J. Food Sci. Tech. 46 (2011) 2513–2519.
31. S.K. Yeap, N. Mohd Ali, H. Mohd Yusof, N.B. Alitheen, B.K. Beh, W.Y. Ho, S.P. Koh, K. Long, Antihyperglycemic effects of fermented and nonfermented mung bean extracts on alloxan-induced-diabetic mice, J. Biomed. Biotechnol. 2012 (2012) 285430.
32. J. Baudry, H. Lelong, S. Adriouch, C. Julia, B. Allès, S. Hercberg, M. Touvier, D. Lairon, P. Galan, E. Kesse-Guyot, Association between organic food consumption and metabolic syndrome: crosssectional results from the NutriNet-Santé study, Eur. J. Nutr. (2017), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00394-017-1520-1>.
33. P.B. Leite, A.R. Dâmaso, V.S. Poli, R.B. Sanches, S.G.A. Silva, J.P.N. Fidalgo, M.A. Nascimento, C.A.M. de Oliveira, D.A. Caranti, Long-term interdisciplinary therapy decreases symptoms of binge eating disorder

- and prevalence of metabolic syndrome in adults with obesity, *Nutr. Res.* 40 (2017) 57–64. [79] M. Yimam, P. Jiao, M. Hong, L. Brownell, Y.C. Lee, H.J. Kim, J.B. Nam, M.R. Kim, Q.A. Jia, A botanical composition from *Morus alba*, *Ilex paraguariensis*, and *Rosmarinus officinalis* for body weight management, *J. Med. Food.* (2017)
34. B.L. Luhovyy, R.C. Mollard, S. Panahi, M.F. Nunez, F. Cho, G.H. Anderson, Canned navy bean consumption reduces metabolic risk factors associated with obesity, *Can. J. Diet Pract. Res.* 76 (2015) 33–37.
35. R.R. Hafidh, A.S. Abdulmir, F. AbuBakar, Z. Sekawi, F. Jahansheri, F.A. Jalilian, Novel antiviral activity of mung bean sprouts against respiratory syncytial virus and herpes simplex virus –1: an in vitro study on virally infected Vero and MRC-5 cell lines, *BMC Complement. Altern. Med.* 15 (2015) 179.
36. J. Luo, W. Cai, T. Wu, B. Xu, Phytochemical distribution in hull and cotyledon of adzuki bean (*Vigna angularis* L.) and mung bean (*Vigna radiata* L.) and their contribution to antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antidiabetic activities, *Food Chem.* 201 (2016) 350–360.
37. J.S. Yook, K.A. Kim, M. Kim, Y.S. Cha, Black adzuki bean (*Vigna angularis*) attenuates high-fat diet-induced colon inflammation in mice, *J. Med. Food* 20 (2017) 367–375.
38. P. Correa, Epidemiological correlations between diet and cancer frequency, *Cancer Res.* 41 (1981) 3685–3689.
39. P.N. Singh, G.E. Fraser, Dietary risk factors for colon cancer in a low-risk population, *Am. J. Epidemiol.* 148 (1998) 761–774.
40. L.N. Kolonel, J.H. Hankin, A.S. Whittemore, A.H. Wu, R.P. Gallagher, L.R. Wilkens, E.M. John, G.R. Howe, D.M. Dreon, D.W. West, R.S. Paffenbarger, Vegetables, fruits, legumes and prostate cancer: a multi ethnic case-control study, *Cancer Epidemiol. Biomark. Prev.* 9 (2000) 795–804.
41. J.S. Hughes, Potential contribution of dry bean dietary fiber to health, *Food Tech.* 45 (1991) 122–126.
42. D.B. Thompson, Strategies for the manufacture of resistant starch, *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 11 (2000) 245–253.
43. L.A. Hangen, M.R. Bennink, Consumption of black beans and navy beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) reduced azoxymethane-induced colon cancer in rats, *Nutr. Cancer.* 44 (2003) 60–65.
44. C.A. Patterson, H. Maskus, C. Dupasquier, Pulse crops for health, *Cereals Foods World* 54 (2009) 108–113.

HOW TO CITE: Ashwini Pandav , Nilesh Chougule , Suchay Bangar , Formulation And Evaluation Of Suntan Lotion From Mung Bean (*Vigna Radiata*) Extract, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 8, 3405-3414. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13337517>

